

EFFECT OF STRESSORS ON PRIMARY HEADACHE

Bozorov Shakhobjon Ismatovich

Bukhara State Medical university

<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2366-0470>

Tolibov Dilshod Sirojovich

Tashkent Medical Academy

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ANNOTATION: The article describes the importance of various stress factors observed in primary headache, their effect on the body, as well as the development of preventive measures.

Key words: Primary headache, stress, clinical significance, mild, moderate, high, prevalence.

Relevance: Chronic pain and stress this severe headache is the main pain syndrome associated with physical and nervous stress. 90% of the population experiences episodes of this pathology during their lifetime. Headache attacks can be caused by:

* nervous stress;

• sitting at the computer for a long time;

* physical overload • * sleep disorders.

The pain is bilateral and localized in the frontoparietal or occipital region, less often completely covering the entire surface of the cerebral part of the skull. Pain syndrome is characterized by pressure, pain, or explosion. Unpleasant sensations appear gradually, and also gradually decrease. The duration of an episode of severe headaches is from several hours to several days. The causes and mechanisms of the development of pathology (chronic pain and stress) are not fully understood until now. Usually, an episode of tension headaches is accompanied by an increase in the tone of the muscles of the head. The sign was formerly known as the "neurasthenic helmet". However, muscle tension is not the leading mechanism for the development of pain. In addition, in some patients, episodes go away without strengthening the cranial muscles.

Stress (English: stress — "pressure", "tension", "tension") is a state of extreme excitement, nervousness, which occurs as a result of strong influences in humans and animals. Stress is a non-specific reaction of the body caused by various extreme factors accompanied by a violation of homeostasis, and is characterized by stereotypical changes in the functioning of the nervous and endocrine systems. A non-specific neurogormonal reaction that develops in relation to various effects in the body. the term "stress" is coined by Canadian pathologist G. Celje described and introduced medicine (1936). Physical (hot, cold, traumatic, etc.) and psychic (fear, harsh sound, extreme joy) stressors are distinguished. The body develops adaptive biochemical and physiological changes aimed at overcoming the influence of these factors, which depend on the strength of the stressor, the duration of action, the physiological system and mental state of a person or animal. The positive or negative effects of stress on the body depend on the body's reaction to this stressor. The amount of catecholamines in the brain is of great importance in controlling all changes in the body. Most often, the development of the disease in one way or another depends on the neurovegetative state and

its reactions characteristic of various types of stress. Thus, the study of adaptation options on the example of the reactivity of brain metabolism under physical and emotional stress, the forecast of the rehabilitation period of reconstructive operations on the main arteries of the head of adaptation characteristics, primary headaches and other functional diseases of the nervous system, a very urgent scientific and practical task is visible.

Materials and methods

The study involved 110 outpatients and inpatients with primary headaches between the ages of 18 and 45 in Group 1 and patients being treated with a 1-2 level diagnosis of Dissirculatory encephalopathy for control using an “accepted stress” Scale Test. The examination involves the study of the standard neurological, emotional and personal condition.

A score of 0 to 13 is considered mild stress.

A score of 14 to 26 minutes is considered an average stress.

A score of 27 to 40 beats per minute is considered a highly perceived stress.

Results of the study: it can be seen that when we conducted the “accepted stress determining scale” test, the mild, moderate and high stresses in groups of patients with primary headaches gave a high result. In groups of patients with dyscirculatory encephalopathy 1-2 levels, however, this indicator formed a low result.

Conclusion: in place of the conclusion, it should be said that stress factors in primary headaches made up a higher causative agent compared to the 1-2 level of Dyscirculatory encephalopathy. Thus, the Prevention of stress factors in primary headaches, early diagnosis is important in improving the quality of life of the patient, maintaining work productivity, while the early treatment and the return of preventive measures to the road are prevented by various types of headaches that occur in the patient.

Patients should receive from preventive measures the correct implementation of the agenda, outdoor walks, labor hygiene (regular ventilation of the room, breaks during work hours), normalization of sleep, diet, diet and food should contain a sufficient amount of minerals and vitamins. All sorts of painkillers are temporary only give us a slight improvement in the

condition, but cannot lose the underlying cause. That is why patients with headaches and various stress factors meet the appropriate specialist (neurologist, Psychoneurologist, psychiatrist) should receive the necessary recommendations.

References:

1. Bozorov Shakhobjon Ismatovich "MODERN DIAGNOSTIC METHODS OF SLEEP DISORDERS IN PRIMARY HEADACHES" IBAST/Volume 3, Issue 6, June./2023./INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY//.C 926-929.
2. Tolibov Dilshod Sirojovich., Bozorov Shaxobjon Ismat o'gli. Sleep Disturbances in Primary Headaches Vol. 1 No. 4 (2022): //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH SYSTEMS AND MEDICAL SCIENCES// C 93-96.
3. Bozorov Shaxobjon Ismatovich // BIRLAMCHI BOSH OG'RIQLARIDAGI UYQU BUZILISHLARINING KLINIK AHAMIYATI VA TARQALGANLIK DARAJASI №3 2023 // JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGY AND RESEARCH //. C 86-88.83
4. Bozorov Shaxobjon Ismat o'gli, Tolibov Dilshod Sirojovich. //REDUCED CONCENTRATION OF ATTENTION IN PRIMARY HEADACHES//.Journal NEW DAY IN MEDICINE. Entered 20.07.2023. 8 (58) 2023. C 192-195.
6. Tolibov Dilshod Sirojovich., Bozorov Shaxobjon Ismat o'gli. Sleep Disturbances in Primary Headaches Vol. 1 No. 4 (2022): //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH SYSTEMS AND MEDICAL SCIENCES// C 93-96.
16. Ахмедова Д. Б. //СУРУНКАЛИ ЗЎРИҚИШДАГИ БОШ ОҒРИҚЛАРИДА БЕМОР НЕЙРОПСИХОЛОГИК ҲОЛАТИГА ДАВОЛАШ ЧОРАЛАРИНИНГ ТАЪСИРИНИ ҚИЁСИЙ БАҲОЛАШ //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 408-413.
17. Akhmedova, D. B., & Khodjiyeva, D. T. (2021). //Improvement of the algoritm for the use of hirudotherapy for the prevention of chronic tension headache.// American journal of medicine and medical science, 2(11),69-70.
18. Bahodirovna, A. D. (2021).// Frequency of observation of anxiety and depression in the diagnosis of primary headaches.//Art of Medicine. International Medical Scientific Journal, 1(2).
19. Ахмедова, Д. Б. (2020). // Бирламчи бош оғриқларини амбулатор шароитда ташхислашдаги хатоликлар.//ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ, 1(4).conference., ISSN 2515-8260 Volume 07, Issue 07, 2021. – С. 49-55.
- Kakhorovna, S. N. (2022). Features of neurorehabilitation itself depending on the pathogenetic course of repeated strokes, localization of the stroke focus and the structure of neurological deficit.
15. Qahharovna, S. N. (2023). Thromboocclusive Lesions of the Bronchocephalic Arteries: Treatment Options and Phytotherapy Options. AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT, 2(2), 41-46.
16. Salomova, N. K. (2022). Risk factors for recurrent stroke. Polish journal of science N, 52, 33-35.
17. Salomova, N. K. (2023). KAITA ISCHEMIC INSULTLARNING CLINIC POTOGENITIC HUSUSIYATLARINI ANIKLASH. Innovations in Technology and Science Education, 2(8), 1255-1264.

18. Salomova, N. K. (2021). Features of the course and clinical and pathogenetic characteristics of primary and recurrent strokes. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 249-253.
19. Rakhmatova, S. N., & Salomova, N. K. (2021). Kaita Takrorlanuvchi Ischemic Va Hemorrhagic Stroke Bemorlarni Erta Rehabilitation Kilishni Optimallashtirish. *Journal Of Neurology And Neurosurgical Research*, 2(4).
20. Salomova, N. K. (2022). RISK FACTORS FOR CEREBROVASCULAR DISEASE AND THE BENEFICIAL PROPERTY OF UNABI IN PREVENTION. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(2), 811-817.
21. Rakhmatova, D. I., & Sanoeva, M. J. (2018). Clinical course of facial nerve neuropathy in patients with comorbid condition. *International Journal of Research*, 4, 532-539.
22. Rakhmatova, D. I. (2020). Forecasting of complications of facial nerve neuropathy according to the results of electroneuromyography. *World journal of pharmaceutical research*, 1547-1555.
23. Rakhmatova, D. I. (2020). Opportunities of acupuncture in treatment of facial nerve neuropathy. *European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine*, 7(7), 567-572.
24. Рахматова, Д. И. (2022). Эффективность нейротрофической терапии сертозина при ишемическом инсульте. *Журнал неврологии и нейрохирургических исследований*, 3(1).
25. Рахматова, Д. И. (2019). Нетрадиционные методы терапии невропатии лицевого нерва на разных этапах развития заболевания. *Проблемы биологии и медицины*, 2(107), 180-183.
26. Рахматова, Д. И. (2022). Новые Возможности Оценки Лечения У Больных С Невропатией Лицевого Нерва Коморбидных С Сахарным Диабетом. *AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI*, 1(7), 38-43.
27. Рахматова, Д. И. (2021). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ НЕЙРОВИЗУАЛИЗАЦИОННОГО МЕТОДА ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ В ДИАГНОСТИКЕ ОСЛОЖНЁННЫХ ФОРМ НЕВРОПАТИИ ЛИЦЕВОГО НЕРВА. *ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ*, 2(3).
28. Gaffarova, V. F. (2021). Clinic-eeg correlation somatogenous of conditioned febrile seizures in children. *International Journal of Human Computing Studies*, 3(1), 114-116.
29. Furqatovna, G. V. (2023). Evaluate the Neuropsychological, Clinical-Neurological and Neurophysiological Characteristics of Febrile and Afebrile Seizures. *AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT*, 2(2), 187-192.
- 6.Gaffarova V.F. Method for prediction of psycho-speech disorders during febril conversions in children.//*ScienceAsia* 48 2022. -P. 951-955 (Scopus)
7. Sadullayev D.I., Gaffarova V.F. Cognitive disorders in patients with acute cerebrovascular accident and arterial hypertension.// *Amaliy va tibbiyot fanlar jurnali* 2022.-P. 293-295.
- 8.Gaffarova V.F. Early prevention of psycho-speech disorders during febril conversions in children.// *European journal of innovation in nonformal education*. Volume 2 Issue 11 November 2022. -P. 74-79.
- 9.Gaffarova V.F. Aspects of febril conversions in children's neurology.// *European journal of innovation in nonformal education*. Volume 2 Issue 12 December 2022. -P. 77-81.
- 10.Гаффарова В.Ф. Болаларда фебрил тутқаноқнинг клиника, диагностикаси ва фебрил тутқаноқ қайталанишига олиб келувчи хавф омиллари.// *Jurnal of Advanced Research and Stability*. Volume: 02 Issue: 11/ Dec-2022 .P 394-401.

30. Zavkiddinova, D. H. (2023). Features of the Course of Cognitive Dysfunction in Patients with Type II Diabetes Mellitus. AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT, 2(3), 53-55.
31. Davronova, H. (2023). COGNITIVE DISORDERS IN TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 3(5), 901-906.
- MLATurakulovich, Tukhtaev Ilkhom. "EVALUATION OF EFFICIENCY OF ACCAPUNCTURE THERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC STROKE." British Medical Journal 1.1.2 (2021).
- APATurakulovich, T. I. (2021). EVALUATION OF EFFICIENCY OF ACCAPUNCTURE THERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC STROKE. British Medical Journal, 1(1.2)